

THE COMPARISON OF ADVERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the similarities and differences between English and Uzbek adverbs, focusing on their functions, classifications, formation, degrees of comparison, syntactic placement, and cultural influences. While both languages share the fundamental role of adverbs in modifying verbs, adjectives, and other adverbs, they differ significantly in their morphological and syntactic approaches. By highlighting these similarities and differences, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of adverbs in both linguistic systems and offers practical insights for language learners

Adverbs are an integral part of language, adding precision and depth to communication by modifying verbs, adjectives, and other adverbs. They answer questions such as how, when, where, and to what extent. In both English and Uzbek, adverbs enrich sentences by expressing manner, place, time, frequency, and degree. However, the two languages differ in how adverbs are formed, positioned, and classified. Adverbs in both English and Uzbek share the fundamental role of modifying other parts of speech [3, 15-23]. For instance, in English, the adverb quickly modifies the verb in "She walks quickly," whereas in Uzbek, the adverb tez fulfills the same function in "U tez yuradi." Thus, adverbs in both languages enhance the meaning of verbs, adjectives, and other adverbs. In addition, adverbs can provide information about the intensity or extent of an action. For example, in English, "very softly" intensifies the degree of softly. Similarly, in Uzbek, "juda yumshoq" conveys the same meaning. Although the two languages achieve this effect differently, the core function remains consistent.

Both English and Uzbek categorize adverbs based on their semantic roles. English adverbs fall into several categories, such as manner (quickly, slowly), place (here, there), time (yesterday, tomorrow), frequency (often, never), and degree (very, extremely). Similarly, Uzbek adverbs (ravishlar) are classified into manner (tez, sekin), place (bu yerda, u yerda), time (kecha, bugun), frequency (har doim, kamdan-kam), and degree (nihoyatda, juda). Although the categories align conceptually, Uzbek adverbs often reflect cultural nuances and practical contexts unique to the language [6, 89-93].

When it comes to word formation, English and Uzbek employ different strategies. Many English adverbs are formed by adding the suffix -ly to adjectives, such as quick → quickly or happy → happily. However, there are irregular adverbs like fast or well that do not follow this

pattern. In Uzbek, adverbs often retain the same form as adjectives. For example, *tez* serves as both an adjective (*tez mashina* – a fast car) and an adverb (*tez yuradi* – walks quickly). Additionally, some adverbs are formed using suffixes like *-cha* or *-day*, as in *qushday uchmoq* (to fly like a bird). Thus, while English relies on morphological markers such as *-ly*, Uzbek relies more heavily on contextual cues to distinguish adverbs from adjectives. For instance, English speakers can immediately identify an adverb by its *-ly* ending, while Uzbek speakers rely on the word's position and meaning within the sentence.

Both languages express degrees of comparison, but they do so differently. Degrees of comparison in English are formed by adding *-er* and *-est* to short adverbs (e.g., *faster*, *fastest*) or by using *more* and *most* with longer adverbs (e.g., *more carefully*, *most carefully*). For example, "She sings more beautifully than him" illustrates the comparative form. In Uzbek, the suffix *-roq* is added to form the comparative degree (e.g., *tezroq* – faster), while the prefix *eng* is used for the superlative (e.g., *eng tez* – the fastest). For instance, "U undan tezroq yuguradi" corresponds to the English sentence "He runs faster than him." Although both languages share the concept of comparison, their morphological tools differ. English comparisons often depend on word length and syllable count, while Uzbek relies on consistent suffix and prefix additions.

The syntactic placement of adverbs varies between English and Uzbek. Adverbs can occupy different positions in a sentence in English. For example, at the beginning: "Yesterday, she arrived late." In the middle: "She always arrives on time." At the end: "She arrived late yesterday." The flexibility of placement allows English adverbs to emphasize different aspects of the sentence, depending on the speaker's intent. In Uzbek, adverbs typically appear before the verb they modify, as in "U kecha kech keldi" (She arrived late yesterday). However, word order in Uzbek is more flexible, allowing adverbs to shift based on emphasis or stylistic choice. This flexibility contrasts with the relatively fixed positions of adverbs in English. For example, in Uzbek poetry and literature, authors often place adverbs creatively to maintain rhythm and rhyme, a stylistic feature less common in English [2, 380-385].

Both languages use intensifiers to modify adverbs and adjectives. Words like *very*, *too*, and *quite* enhance the degree of an action or quality in English, as in "She speaks very softly." Similarly, words such as *juda* and *nihoyatda* perform a similar role in Uzbek, as in "U juda sokin gapiradi" (She speaks very softly). While the specific words differ, their functions are remarkably similar. Intensifiers in both languages add emphasis and are frequently used in spoken and written communication to convey stronger emotions or highlight particular points. For example, the phrase "extremely important" in English mirrors the Uzbek phrase "nihoyatda muhim," both of which underscore the significance of the subject.

Lastly, cultural context shapes adverb usage in both languages. For instance, Uzbek includes adverbs like *oqibatda* (eventually, often with a moral undertone) that reflect cultural values, such as the importance of patience and perseverance. Conversely, English adverbs like *virtually* or *technically* reflect a focus on abstraction and modernity. These differences highlight how language and culture influence adverbial expressions. Additionally, English, influenced by global communication and technology, has adopted numerous adverbs from other languages, whereas Uzbek retains a more traditional set of adverbs deeply rooted in its cultural and historical context. For example, the Uzbek adverb "xotirjamlik bilan" (calmly, with peace) reflects a cultural emphasis on composure and mindfulness, values that resonate deeply within Uzbek society.

In conclusion, English and Uzbek adverbs share many similarities in their core functions, classifications, and roles in modifying other parts of speech. However, they differ in formation, degrees of comparison, and syntactic positioning. By understanding these similarities and

differences, language learners can enhance their grasp of both languages. Ultimately, the study of adverbs reveals the richness of linguistic diversity and the shared need for precision and nuance in human communication. Moreover, exploring the cultural dimensions of adverb usage underscores the interconnectedness of language and identity, offering valuable insights into how people from different linguistic backgrounds perceive and articulate their world.

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